

Azolla at the frontier of climate change: A plant-based intervention for Sub-Saharan agriculture

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Advancing climate change and desertification threaten agriculture and livelihoods in semi-arid regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa. *Azolla*, a fast-growing aquatic fern, offers a versatile solution through its value as livestock feed and crop fertiliser. Its rapid biomass production, nitrogen-fixing symbiosis, and ability to grow on wastewater make it well suited for scalable climate-adaptation strategies. We introduce the *Azolla* Vertical Overflow Reactor (AVOR), a solar-powered system engineered for continuous biomass production under Sahelian conditions, that simultaneously generates purified water as a by-product. This perspective demonstrates the potential of *Azolla*-based solutions to enhance food security and ecological resilience in agriculturally marginal lands.

The *Azolla* Event Revisited

Approximately 49 million years ago, during the Eocene epoch, a significant biological phenomenon unfolded around Earth's North Pole. Geological and micro-paleontological evidence suggests that the Arctic Ocean, at that time more geographically enclosed than today, exhibited reduced salinity due to increased freshwater influx, creating conditions favourable for the proliferation of the aquatic freshwater fern *Azolla* [1]. This expansive bloom, known as the *Azolla* Event, refers to a period during which vast quantities of *Azolla* proliferated across the Arctic Ocean, forming persistent mats over large areas [1, 2, 3]. The resulting biomass accumulation is hypothesised to have contributed substantially to the long-term drawdown of atmospheric CO₂ through biological carbon sequestration, exerting an important biological influence on global climate dynamics during the Eocene [1, 2]. While the magnitude and duration of the *Azolla* Event remain subject of ongoing debate [4], the Event has shed light on the extraordinary growth capabilities of what is often referred to as the fastest-growing fern on Earth. In contemporary contexts, *Azolla* blooms continue to capture attention due to the plant's unique biological features, rapid growth performance, and multifaceted utility in sustainable development.

Azolla Biology

Azolla is a genus of small, aquatic ferns distributed across temperate and tropical freshwater systems worldwide. Its biological productivity is partially explained by a unique endosymbiosis with the nitrogen-fixing cyanobacterium *Nostoc azollae*, which resides in specialised leaf cavities [5, 6, 7]. This obligate symbiosis allows *Azolla* to fix atmospheric nitrogen independently, enabling colonisation of nitrogen-poor waters and yielding biomass with comparatively high protein content [5, 8]. In addition to symbiotic nitrogen fixation, *Azolla* propagates efficiently through vegetative fragmentation, allowing rapid surface coverage and high growth rates under suitable environmental conditions [8, 9]. These characteristics have driven substantial research into its potential applications, including its use as a bio-fertiliser, feed supplement for livestock, and its role as a biological agent for phytoremediation [8, 9, 10]. Experimental studies also demonstrate that *Azolla* can effectively remove excess phosphorus, nitrogen compounds, and several heavy metals from contaminated water bodies [11].

Azolla Growth Conditions

Azolla ferns have been reported to double their biomass within 2-5 days when grown in favourable conditions [12, 13]. Typical fresh-weight yields in peer-reviewed studies range between 0.3 to 1.5 kg m⁻² week⁻¹ (corresponding to 30-150 g dry weight m⁻² week⁻¹), depending on species and experimental conditions [12, 13, 15]. Reported yields above these values primarily originate from non-peer-reviewed institutional reports and were therefore excluded here. The fern grows optimally in shallow water columns of approximately 5-10 cm, allowing fronds to float and facilitate gas exchange at the water surface [13]. Light requirements for optimal growth typically fall in the range of 100-200 μmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹, while higher irradiance can lead to photo-inhibition, particularly in species adapted to shaded environments [13, 14]. Temperature tolerance varies among species. *Azolla pinnata*, one of the more heat-tolerant taxa within the genus, exhibits optimal growth between roughly 25-35 °C, with substantial declines in growth below 15 °C and evidence of heat stress above approximately 35 °C [14, 15]. *Azolla* generally thrives under high relative humidity, with optimal growth seen around 85-90 % relative humidity; growth rates decline when humidity drops below ~60 % [12]. Optimal growth further requires mildly acidic to neutral pH (5.5-7.5) and sufficient phosphorus availability, with concentrations below 0.2-0.5 mg L⁻¹ often limiting growth in experimental cultures [12, 15]. Nitrogen supplementation is generally unnecessary due to the presence of *N. azollae*. Moreover, peer-reviewed studies have shown that species such as *A. pinnata* and *A. filiculoides* can grow effectively in nutrient-rich wastewater, simultaneously producing biomass while capturing pollutants [10, 12, 15].

Sahel Africa: A frontier Of Climate Change

The Sahel region of Africa spans the southern border of the Saharan Desert, separating the Saharan desert in the north and tropical savanna in the south. While mean temperatures throughout the region are generally warm, the climate is diverse, with humidity and precipitation decreasing toward the northern part of the region [16]. Mean annual temperatures generally range from 21 °C to 31 °C [16] and mean annual precipitation falls between 10 mm in northern Niger to 3800 mm in western Cameroon [16]. The region is home to a population of about 300 million people, roughly 60% of whom rely on agriculture for their livelihood [17].

Climate change is projected to have severe impacts on the Sahel region. Under various climate scenarios, the region is expected to experience rising temperatures, more frequent and severe droughts and intensified extremes in precipitation cycles, all of which can lead to widespread crop failure and threaten food security. [18, 19, 20, 21]. Given that most agriculture in Sahel Africa is rain-fed, crop yield is expected to deteriorate. According to a climate risk profile from the Nations High Commission for Refugees, even millet and sorghum, two of the Sahel's most vital food crops, are vulnerable to reduced yields under the stresses imposed by climate change, despite their known resistance to heat and drought [16, 20]. Additionally, unsustainable agricultural practices such as soil mining (the extraction of soil nutrients without replenishment) have degraded soil fertility in the region [22, 23]. Both human and livestock populations are growing rapidly, which not only worsens the issue of soil degradation, but also increases the demand for food production [24]. Thus, there would be significant benefit in year-round, climate and soil fertility independent agricultural infrastructure.

An *Azolla* Based Solution for the Sahel

A technological system that capitalises on *Azolla*'s extraordinary growth potential is uniquely positioned to elevate agricultural production in marginally arid lands like the Sahel. Unlike conventional crops, *Azolla* does not rely on fertile soils. It grows rapidly on shallow water surfaces [9, 10], tolerates nutrient-poor conditions, and requires only sunlight, water, and a set of manageable environmental parameters to sustain high biomass yields [12, 13, 15]. This makes *Azolla* an especially promising candidate for addressing the agricultural needs of regions like the Sahel, where degraded soils, low rainfall, and high temperatures severely limit most conventional forms of cultivation [18, 19, 20, 22, 23]. Combining the challenges of Sahel Africa with the remarkable biology of the *Azolla* genus, we propose a system that leverages the advantages of clonal fern blooms to provide a reliable and sustainable source of essential agricultural products, even during volatile climates and long dry seasons when traditional crops fail.

Livestock Feed

Azolla biomass offers a high-quality supplement for livestock diets, due to its high crude protein content and favourable amino acid composition [9, 25, 26]. Dried *Azolla pinnata* contains 25–30% protein and provides important vitamins, including A and B₁₂ [27]. It is rich in essential minerals, and its low lignin content makes it easily digestible and effective as a feed additive [28]. Feeding trials in ruminants have shown that incorporation of *Azolla* significantly increases average daily muscle gain and can boost milk production by up to 15% [29]. Trials in Burkina Faso have shown that locally cultivated *Azolla*, when constituting up to 10% of broiler feed protein, enhances poultry growth performance significantly [30]. A similar effect has been found by integrating *Azolla* into the diet of lambs in south Sinai, Egypt, leading to substantial weight gain over controls, while reducing feed cost by 22% [31]. Numerous studies have documented the beneficial effects of *Azolla* as a component of animal fodder across species [29, 32, 33, 34]. Because conventional protein-rich feeds such as soybean meal are often imported and costly in regions like the Sahel [35], local *Azolla* cultivation would represent a low-cost, renewable protein source that could improve food security and reduce dependency on external inputs. In many regions of southern Asia, small-scale household *Azolla* systems generate substantial amounts of fresh biomass, contributing to agricultural production as livestock feed or as a locally sourced fertiliser [36]. Expanding these systems into vertical cultivation frameworks could enable biomass production at scales reaching

Figure 1. Schematic representation highlighting the potential and multifaceted impact of *Azolla* cultivation in the Sahel region of Africa.

several tons per hectare per year, thereby supporting broader community-based, agricultural, and ecological applications.

Wastewater Treatment & Phytoremediation

Azolla species have demonstrated a strong capacity for nutrient assimilation in wastewater systems. In constructed wetlands with *Azolla pinnata*, significant removal of phosphorus and chemical oxygen demand (COD) has been documented, along with removal of heavy metals such as zinc (Zn) and lead (Pb) [37]. *Azolla* has also been shown to bioaccumulate other heavy metals, such as cadmium (Cd) and nickel (Ni), achieving up to ~70% removal under certain conditions [38]. In microcosm experiments, *Azolla pinnata* removed 70–94% of mercury (Hg²⁺) and cadmium (Cd²⁺) from water over a period of ~13 days [39]. In addition a 2025 study highlights *Azolla*'s ability to remove chromium (Cr VI) from aqueous solutions, with reported removal efficiencies up to ~70% [40]. The treated water was then used to irrigate broad bean (*Vicia faba*) without adverse effects [40]. These datapoints highlight that *Azolla* could serve a dual role of remediation and resource recovery, producing biomass while purifying water.

Soil Restoration & Bio-fertilisation

The incorporation of *Azolla* biomass into soil can improve soil fertility and organic matter content [36, 41]. Field trials in vegetable cropping systems show that *Azolla* based bio-fertiliser matched or outperformed synthetic urea, increasing lettuce yields by 9% and radish by 14%, while also improving the bio-availability of organic carbon and nitrogen compounds in the soil [41]. In paddy systems, *Azolla* application increases the availability and uptake of N, P, and K in rice, improving soil chemical properties such as cation-exchange capacity (CEC) and organic carbon [42]. Numerous studies demonstrate that *Azolla* decomposition enhances nitrogen mineralization, increases phosphatase activities, and raises soil organic carbon and nutrient levels [37, 38].

Economic Avenues

The cultivation of *Azolla* in Sahelian agro-ecosystems presents a compelling portfolio of economic opportunities. Key avenues include feed substitution, fertiliser replacement, and biomass

valorisation. *Azolla*'s potential to replace conventional protein sources in poultry and ruminant livestock diets offers immediate financial benefit. Its inclusion in feed rations can partially replace soybean meal, an ingredient that is typically imported into Sub-Saharan Africa at significantly higher per-bushel prices than those on U.S. markets. [43]. Given that feed represents over 60% of livestock production expenses in the region [44], local *Azolla* production could markedly improve profit margins for pastoralists and small-scale farmers. Similarly, the economic value of *Azolla* as a nitrogen-rich bio-fertiliser lies in its capacity to substitute synthetic urea [41], reducing input costs and enhancing soil health for local farms. In Sub-Saharan Africa over 80% of synthetic urea is imported [45] at very high cost, roughly four times more expensive than European market prices [46]. Beyond its agricultural applications, emerging research highlights *Azolla*'s potential as a feedstock for bioplastics, paper pulp, or biofuel precursors [47]. With annual biomass yields substantially higher than those of conventional crops, *Azolla* represents a particularly valuable resource in contexts where the availability of fertile land is limited [48]. Cumulatively, these avenues point to *Azolla* as a multi-functional economic asset. Its ability to displace costly inputs, generate sellable byproducts, and support circular agricultural models positions it not only as a carbon-negative ecological tool, but as a driver of rural economic resilience under intensifying climate pressures.

Azolla Vertical Overflow Reactor (AVOR)

To align the potential of *Azolla* with the needs of the Sahel, we aimed to develop a technological system capable of maintaining stable and suitable growth conditions for the fern within the harsh and variable environmental context of Sub-Saharan Africa. Inspired by the continuous plant growth of the Azolla-Event, we placed the *Azolla* fern at the centre of our system design, harnessing its vegetative propagation to generate ongoing growth through photosynthesis and carbon fixation. The general design of the AVOR system (Fig. 2, 3) was guided by three principal considerations: (I) maximising the available surface area for *Azolla* cultivation, (II) minimising operational and maintenance requirements, and (III) mitigating environmental stress factors posed by the Sahel climate, with a special emphasis on heat stress.

A guiding objective was to standardise the AVOR system through the use of simple mechanisms and widely available commercial components. The structural framework consists primarily of two standard shipping containers, selected for their global availability, structural robustness, and cost-effectiveness. All components were chosen with affordability and accessibility in mind, enabling both large-scale deployment and straightforward replacement in the event of damage. This approach minimises overall system complexity while enhancing maintainability and long-term operational resilience.

Cultivation & Yield Estimation

Because *Azolla* proliferates on the water surface and requires only minimal water depth, the primary spatial parameter for production is horizontal area rather than volume. Consequently, each Azolla Cultivation Module (ACM) (Fig. 4) was designed as a shallow, large-format growing box measuring 70 × 50 cm with a height of 12 cm and 5 cm space between two layers (Fig. 3, 4). This compact stacking design fulfills two key functions: it maximises the available surface area within the reactor and simultaneously helps to retain evaporated water in the narrow spaces between the cultivation modules, increasing the relative humidity within the system. The upper container accommodates 240 ACMs, resulting in a total effective

Figure 2. 3D Model of the AVOR system. Birds-eye view (A) Side view with partial cross-section (B), revealing the interior gravity-flow gutter system, that channels overflow into the *Azolla* collection tank.

cultivation area of 84 m² within a total system volume of 33 m³. (Fig. 2, 3) Assuming a suboptimal growth rate of 0.3-0.6 (kg m⁻² day⁻¹), the AVOR system is expected to yield approximately 25-50kg wet weight of *Azolla* per week. Maximal yields of >100kg per week could be achieved if physiologically optimal growing conditions are maintained.

Gravity Harvest

The harvesting concept underlines this emphasis on simplicity. The system relies predominantly on gravity-driven flow: water is released from an elevated grey-water reservoir (Fig. 5) into each growing box, gradually overflowing the individual ACM. This overflow carries a portion of the *Azolla* biomass through a series of gutters into a sieve, where the biomass is collected

Figure 3. Exploded view of the AVOR-System including annotations.

(Fig. 2, 3). While most of the *Azolla* is flushed out during this process, the water volume is carefully calibrated so that only about 80% of the water surface is emptied, leaving a residual portion of the *Azolla* in the ACM to serve as seed for the next growth cycle. Excess water is directed through an additional filter into a clean-water tank, accessible via a tap, ensuring both efficient biomass harvesting and purified water collection (Fig. 2, 3). Only one pump is required to refill the elevated grey water

reservoir, operating for short intervals each day. Because refill time is non-critical, the pump can be of low capacity. Outflow from the grey-water reservoir is regulated by a single valve operating on predefined intervals. Thus, the entire harvesting mechanism contains only two moving components, enhancing reliability and reducing long-term maintenance needs.

Water Supply

The primary limiting factor for the AVOR system is water supply, as the plants require fresh, non-saline water for optimal growth. Water scarcity in the region confines the system's placement to riverine areas and deltas surrounding the Niger River, Komadugu Yobe River, Chari-Logone Rivers, or Mekrou River. To avoid depleting these critical water resources, the system is designed to generate purified water as a byproduct of Biomass cultivation. By utilising artificial and plant-based wastewater filtration, the system generates biomass, while simultaneously producing purified water. This dual functionality enhances the system's utility and ensures it does not compete with local communities for vital freshwater resources.

Figure 4. 3D model of one of the 240 Azolla Cultivation Modules (ACM), with annotations and dimensions.

Light Supply

In addition to the indirect sunlight provided by the open system design, each ACM is equipped with LEDs that deliver light in the visual and far-red spectrum to support optimal *Azolla* growth (Fig. 4). The LEDs are programmed to follow a day-night cycle, preventing light stress and maintaining the plant's natural photo-cycle. During periods of elevated temperatures, the excess heat generated by the LEDs is mitigated through the use of auxiliary fans, which enhance airflow and prevent heat buildup within the system. (Fig. 2, 3).

Temperature

Temperature regulation constitutes one of the central challenges in ensuring consistent *Azolla* growth, particularly given the high ambient temperatures characteristic of the Sahel and the additional heat generated by the LED lighting. Four complementary strategies were implemented to mitigate thermal stress. First, a white container with open sidewalls was selected to avoid greenhouse warming within the system and allow for thermal energy to escape through natural ventilation and convective airflow (Fig. 2, 3). Second, a double-roof configuration, often used in vernacular architecture in hot climates, was installed above the containers. This secondary roof provides shade, preventing direct solar radiation from heating the primary structure, while the air gap between the two roofs facilitates wind-driven heat dissipation (Fig. 2, 3). Third, to manage short-term temperature peaks in the absence of natural wind, auxiliary fans were installed along both sides of the reactor, that can be activated to artificially increase airflow during periods of extreme heat. This setup helps expel hot air from the system and enhances evaporative cooling within the ACMs (Fig. 2, 3). A final measure for mitigating heat stress involves cooling the water within the grey water reservoir through a system inspired by the "Zeer Pot," a simple

evaporative cooling technique that leverages the naturally high temperatures and low ambient humidity characteristic of the Sub-Saharan environment [49]. In this design, the grey-water reservoir is surrounded by a ring of sand contained within a permeable, durable fabric such as woven polypropylene. (Fig. 5). During operation, when the reservoir is refilled, it is intentionally allowed to overflow slightly, enabling water to percolate into the surrounding sand. As the moisture evaporates from the sand, the water reservoir is cooled through evaporative heat loss. This passive cooling mechanism reduces the system's water temperature and contributes to maintaining a temperature range conducive to *Azolla* growth.

AVOR-System: Costs, Maintenance & Automation

Minimising cost and maintenance was a key consideration in the design of the AVOR system. To enhance efficiency, components are integrated to serve multiple functions, supporting both the functionality and longevity of the system. Sunlight is absorbed by the photovoltaic panels to charge the batteries while simultaneously providing shading for the primary system. (Fig. 2, 3) Water filters remove debris and waste before they enter the system, preserving pump performance and protecting the system's functional integrity, while also providing three artificial layers of water filtration in addition to the biological filtration performed by the *Azolla* plants. The AVOR system is engineered to operate autonomously, requiring virtually no human intervention. *Azolla* biomass accumulates in the 0.33 m³ collection box, which can hold over 200 kg of *Azolla*. Filtered water is collected in the clean water tank at the base of the system (Fig. 2, 3). Under normal conditions, the only required human intervention is the harvest of *Azolla* and the collection of purified water once every 1-2 weeks to maintain optimal operation. In the event of a malfunction or damage, operation can be easily halted by flushing the system, whereby all ACM are emptied. The system's simple components and open-container layout allow easy access to the individual ACMs if recalibrations or repairs are required (Fig. 2, 3).

The projected cost of the AVOR system depends on the scale of implementation, as mass production of custom components, such as the ACM and the collection tank, can substantially reduce overall manufacturing expenses. Because the system relies on solar panels for electricity, which must be of high quality to operate efficiently under intense sunlight, the electrical components are expected to account for the largest portion of the total cost. By combining low-cost materials with high-quality essential technical components, rough estimates

Figure 5. 3D model of the grey-water reservoir evaporative cooling system: Top view (A), side view (B), and exploded view with annotations (C).

suggest that a single AVOR system would cost between \$20,000 and \$50,000, depending on its configuration and scale of deployment.

AVOR-System: Prospects

Harnessing *Azolla*'s biological potential offers promising opportunities to address the challenges of the Sahel at multiple scales (Fig. 1). The AVOR system generates valuable agricultural biomass and bio-fertiliser, while simultaneously providing purified water for the local community. In addition to supporting existing agricultural systems, the cultivation and use of *Azolla* may open new economic avenues for local communities by integrating sustainable carbon-negative commodities into the local economy. Furthermore, by stabilising soils and enriching degraded landscapes, *Azolla*-based bioremediation efforts could not only contribute to increased crop yields, but may also combat desertification through the improvement of soil health and support of the local plant fauna. This perspective hopes to underline the potential of *Azolla* cultivation in the Sahel as a holistic strategy to promote agricultural sustainability, community resilience, and environmental restoration.

Challenges To The AVOR System

Despite its considerable potential, the AVOR system is subject to a range of operational, environmental, and socio-economic challenges that may constrain its long-term effectiveness. Foremost among these is the reliable maintenance of suitable growth conditions, particularly temperature and humidity regulation. *Azolla* exhibits strong thermal sensitivity and demands a narrow temperature window for optimal productivity [14, 15]. Ensuring appropriate humidity and light levels within the growth reactor presents a challenge, as the LED lighting, essential for optimal photosynthesis, constitutes a

thermal load in addition to the elevated ambient temperatures of the Sahel. We recognize that the ventilation-based temperature control, aimed at mitigating the thermal load inside the reactor, will temporarily compromise optimal humidity levels within the system. Both passive and active cooling strategies may prove insufficient during periods of weather extremes, and system operation may become compromised or untenable during the hottest months of the year. The advancement of desertification may further reduce operational stability, as dust storms, high evaporation rates, and fluctuating nutrient levels in the rivers may disrupt growth dynamics or increase maintenance demands.

Although the system is intentionally designed for low mechanical complexity, failures in pumps, valves, or ventilation components, combined with limited access to replacement parts and technical infrastructure, pose meaningful risks to continuous operation. This lack of infrastructure poses an additional challenge in regards to placement and distribution. The required proximity to water sources dramatically limits the area in which this system can be implemented. This poses challenges in regards to the distribution of the harvest, as some members of the local community may have to engage in long commutes to benefit from the AVOR systems. Beyond these physical and infrastructural constraints, biological pressures such as pest infestations, algal contamination, or disruptions to the *Azolla-Nostoc* symbiosis represent additional vulnerabilities, particularly under environmentally stressed conditions [50, 51, 52]. Ultimately, successful implementation will require strong community engagement, adequate training, and integration with existing agricultural and water-management practices. Without sustained local ownership and clear economic incentives, even a technologically robust system may struggle to achieve lasting impact.

Figure 6. Visual representation of the AVOR system operating on marginal lands in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Outlook

The integration of the AVOR system into climate-vulnerable regions offers a promising frontier in sustainable development, environmental restoration, and climate adaptation (Fig. 1). Looking ahead, several avenues of research and implementation warrant further exploration to unlock the full potential of this approach. At the biological level, a deeper mechanistic understanding of species-specific thermal tolerance, symbiont stability, and stress-response pathways will be essential for optimising *Azolla*'s performance under increasingly unpredictable climatic conditions. Equally important is the development of locally adapted protocols, that integrate *Azolla* based commodities into existing agricultural norms. The installation of low-cost sensing technologies could provide critical climate information, to ensure operational optimization and reliable biomass output across seasons.

From a technological standpoint, future work should evaluate how modular cultivation design, such as the AVOR system, could be refined, scaled, and integrated with renewable energy sources, natural water resources, and existing agricultural value chains. Life-cycle assessment and techno-economic analysis will play critical roles in determining system feasibility, long-term resilience, and environmental co-benefits, particularly with respect to water use efficiency and nutrient circularity. Field-based pilot programs across diverse Sahelian microclimates will be essential to validate system performance outside controlled settings, and to identify context-specific constraints that may not be apparent in theoretical or laboratory designs.

Equally central to the system's future is its socio-economic integration. The success of *Azolla*-based interventions will depend not only on technological reliability, but also on their alignment with local livelihood strategies, governance structures, and cultural practices. Participatory design approaches, co-developed with farmers, pastoralists, women's groups, and local authorities, will be critical in fostering community ownership. This will reduce barriers to adoption, and ensure equitable distribution of benefits. Emerging markets for bio-fertilisers, protein-rich feed, and carbon-negative biological commodities further highlight the need for policy frameworks that support local entrepreneurship, capacity building, and sustainable value-chain development.

Taken together, these directions underline that the AVOR system and other *Azolla*-centered technologies have the potential to become transformative tools for climate resilience, provided that biological, technological, and socio-economic considerations advance in parallel. By bridging ecological innovation with local knowledge and adaptive governance, *Azolla*-based systems may ultimately contribute not only to enhanced food and water security but also to broader bioremediation strategies, capable of supporting vulnerable communities in an era of accelerating environmental change.

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Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Germany), the State of Berlin, and the Berlin University Alliance, with particular acknowledgement of the Institute of Experimental Physics at the Freie Universität Berlin for providing laboratory facilities. Special thanks are extended to Dr. Dennis Nürnberg for his mentorship, guidance, and support since the inception of the project. Finally, we wish to express our sincere appreciation to all students who participated in the LivingTechnology Project. Their tireless effort, critical discussions, and rigorous revisions were invaluable. This work would not have been possible without them.

Author contributions

F.G. conceptualised the idea, C.R., J.T., M.S.H. and A.A. contributed to the drafting and revision of the paper, and have approved the final draft thereof.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.